

A Stepped-Care Approach to facilitate Return to Work for Employees with Psychological Distress: Design of a Randomized Controlled Trial.

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Introduction

Psychological distress is highly prevalent among workers and often lead to long-term absenteeism and work disability. Effective elements found in previous researched interventions were to:

- 1) **explicitly focus on return to work (RTW)**¹
- 2) **to take into account the employees' cognition towards RTW**² and
- 3) **to include the workplace environment**^{1,3}

Based on these elements, a stepped-care approach was developed. **The aim** is to present the study design of a randomized controlled trial (RESTART), evaluating the effectiveness and process of implementation of the stepped-care approach on lasting RTW and the implementation process.

Study Population

Participants will be employees of the OHS network, who reported sick for a minimum of 2 weeks and a maximum of 8 weeks. Participants are eligible if they 1) filled in the distress screener based on the Four-Dimensional Symptoms Questionnaire (4DSQ), 2) met the distress criteria and 3) signed informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

- Severe psychiatric disorders
- Treatment for terminal or chronic illness
- Labour dispute with employer

Intervention

The stepped-care approach starts with a **low intensive e-Health program**, followed by a **high intense Participatory Approach** guided by a RTW-coordinator.

The e-Health program has a duration of 6 weeks and is followed independently by the employee. The program is based on psychological principles of **cognitive behavioral therapy** and **problem-solving therapy**.

Aim: To stimulate positive cognitions towards RTW and as preparation for the Participatory Approach.

In case of persistent sickness absence at 6 weeks, the e-Health program is followed by a Participatory Approach (PA). The PA consists of three conversations with the employee and their supervisor.

Aim: To reach consensus on the most important obstacles for RTW, appropriate solutions for these obstacles and a RTW plan in which these solutions are implemented.

Design

A RCT with a 2x2 factorial design and a follow-up of one year. Target N = 170 employees.

Primary outcome: Time to lasting RTW

Secondary outcomes: severity of stress-related symptoms, total sick leave, self-efficacy and self-reported health.

Process evaluation to measure implementation and experiences with the intervention will be conducted. Indicators such as fidelity, dose delivered, reach, recruitment and context will be evaluated.

Discussion

Early intervention that focuses on RTW, the cognition towards RTW despite symptoms and involves the workplace environment, plays a crucial role in managing sickness absence among employees with psychological distress. If effective, the stepped-care approach is relevant for employees, employers and society as a whole.

Strengths: The e-Health program focuses on developing and reinforcing a positive cognition towards RTW and PA is more effective for the group with such a positive cognition – the two interventions complement each other.

Limitations: Potential non-adherence for the e-Health program and PA.

References

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